

D7.9: 2nd Pro-Enrich event annual report

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Executive summary

The Pro-Enrich event annual report is a compendium that documents different communication and dissemination activities conducted within the Pro-Enrich project.

This 2nd edition of the Pro-Enrich event annual covers the period of M13 to M24 and includes consortium meetings (M13 and M18 meetings) and partner participation in relevant events where Pro-Enrich dissemination activities have been conducted.

Due to the corona pandemic, a few planned dissemination activities were unfortunately cancelled or postponed in March and April 2020 (M23-24).

Different types of audiences have been targeted including the general public, the scientific community, industries and relevant networks. Both academic and industry Pro-Enrich partners have contributed significantly to dissemination activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Pro-Enrich event annual report is a compendium that documents different communication and dissemination activities conducted within the Pro-Enrich project. This 2nd edition covers the period M13 to M24. The Pro-Enrich event annual report will be updated again in M36 (3rd and final edition – D7.10). In the following sections, illustrative examples of activities are given for the period M13 to M24. The activities cover consortium meetings, our midterm review meeting, as well as “dissemination activities and events”. For a complete list/overview of events, see the “Dissemination & communication plan” (D7.1 to D7.4).

2. CONSORTIUM MEETINGS

During the second year of the Pro-Enrich project (period M13 to M24) two general assemblies have been conducted in the consortium.

- M13 meeting, May 23rd – 24th, 2019 at Tate & Lyle, Lübeck, Germany
- M18 meeting, November 18th – 19th, 2019, at InnoRenew, Koper, Slovenia

2.1. M13 meeting

The Pro-Enrich 3rd general assembly was hosted by Tate & Lyle in Lübeck, Germany, in May 2019. In addition to managing project progress the program included a tour of the global innovation centre and pilot plant. During this tour, Pro-Enrich partners were updated on food and beverage solutions, sweeteners, stabilisation and functional systems, customer demands, market trends and bio-based solutions. The tour promoted useful discussion among partners about products from Pro-enrich and how they can be included in new sustainable food solutions. Market possibilities for plant-based food products were discussed during a tasting session.

Picture 1. Group photo at M13 meeting May 23rd – 24th 2019 at Tate & Lyle, Lübeck, Germany

Picture 2. The general assembly included a tour of the global innovation centre and pilot plant.

Picture 3. Pro-Enrich partners were updated on food and beverage solutions, sweeteners, stabilisation and functional systems, customer demands, market trends and bio-based solutions. A testing session included plant-based alternatives to meat products.

2.2. M18 meeting

The Pro-Enrich 4th general assembly was hosted by InnoRenew in Koper, Slovenia in November 2019.

In addition to the general information and discussions on the progress of the project, this meeting had a particular focus on exploitation of project results, in order to approach the market for the products that the Pro-Enrich project has identified as key components. This took the form of multiple, product-focused workshops with the goal of determining market requirements, status on results, economic and life cycle analyses and key exploitable results. Agro Business Park facilitated the workshops.

One of the most interesting result came from project partner Natac who presented a hesperidin enriched product with a purity of 60 % reaching market requirements for use in e.g. nutraceuticals. Hesperidin is a flavonoid with antioxidant properties and was obtained from citrus fruit side-streams.

The general assembly also included a tour of InnoRenew lab facilities where technical equipment for biomass analysis was shown. The tour stimulated discussions on how biomass and side-streams in the project should be treated, transported, stored and analysed.

The attending participants also visited project partner Franka Marzi – a small olive processing plant. The visit gave valuable information about raw materials, olive processing and side-streams logistics.

Picture 4. Group photo in the central square of Koper, Slovenia.

Picture 5. During a lab tour at InnoRenew, Matthew Schwarzkopf presented how biomass side-streams can be processed and analysed.

Picture 6. Demonstration of olive processing at project partner Franka Marzi.

3. REVIEW MEETING IN BRUSSELS

In January 2020 the project coordinator and WP leaders were invited for the first periodic project review meeting in Brussels. The review board consisted of BBI project officer Ana Cuadrado and two external review experts. In addition to the project review, the meeting also included a presentation by the “BBI JU communication team”. The input from project officer, external experts and the BBI JU communication team provided valuable input on ways of increasing the impact of the project as well as the results generated in the project.

Picture 7. Group photo from periodic review meeting in Brussels, January 2020. The meeting included project coordinator, WP leaders, project officer and 2 review experts.

4. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES AND EVENTS

Dissemination activities are conducted within Work Package 7 (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation), for which ABP is work package leader and main responsible. The 1st and 2nd Dissemination & communication plans (D7.1 and D7.2) described how to disseminate to the following target groups:

- All target groups (including general public)
- Research and scientific community
- Industries
- Existing networks
- Political organizations

In the following section lists and examples are provided of relevant activities in relation to different target groups.

4.1. All target groups (including the general public)

In the past year Pro-Enrich partners have participated in the following events where the target group has been broad and has included the general public:

- Circular Bioeconomy Days, June 25th – 27th, 2019, Foulum, Denmark (2D)
- Food Festival, Aarhus, September 6th, 2019, Aarhus, Denmark (2D) (Picture 8)
- Welsh Gov H2020 Annual Event, July 4th, 2019, Cardiff, UK (2D)
- Danish Bio-Economy Conference, September 25th, 2019, Sakskøbing, Denmark (2D)

One example of a dissemination activity targeting the general public was Aarhus Food Festival 2019 in Denmark. The festival, which is the largest of its kind in Northern Europe with over 30,000 people visitors, displays the newest trends in the food industry, upcoming food entrepreneurs and new products.

In 2019, a new focus area was introduced on the festival called “Health and Sustainability”. Here the festival attendees could meet start-ups working with sustainable products, new proteins and health, and they could learn more about different projects with the same agenda.

Dissemination manager, Kell Kleiner Andersen had the opportunity to talk to the assembly about alternative proteins and the Pro-Enrich project (Figure 8). The visitors were very interested in seeing the fine protein powder that was extracted from rapeseed in the project.

Due to the corona pandemic the following scheduled event was cancelled:

- Danish Science Festival (Forskningens Døgn), April 22nd, 2019, Denmark (2D)

Picture 8. Dissemination manager Kell Andersen, Agro Business Park presenting Pro-Enrich at Food Festival 2019.

4.2. Research and scientific community

Pro-Enrich partners have participated in events where the main target group has been the research and scientific community. These include:

- Circular Bioeconomy Days, June 25th – 27th, 2019, Foulum Denmark (2E) (Figure 9)
- Food Festival, Aarhus, September 6th, 2019, Denmark (2E)
- Welsh Gov H2020 Annual Event, July 4th, 2019, Cardiff, UK (2E)
- Danish Bio-Economy Conference 2019, September 25th, 2019, Sakskøbing, Denmark (2E) (Figure 10)

One example of a dissemination activity that targeted the research and scientific community was Circular Bioeconomy Days. The international conference Circular Bioeconomy Days 2019 focuses on the worldwide efforts towards a green economy and underlines the importance of the waste hierarchy in supporting the transition to the circular bioeconomy. More than 200 researchers, entrepreneurs, politicians and people from the industry put spotlight on the circular bioeconomy in Viborg, Denmark. The 3-day event in June 2019 focused on the circular bioeconomy as a tool to implement the UN Sustainability Development Goals, and, more precisely, to develop the sustainable proteins of the future. Agro Business Park, as co-organiser of the event, had the opportunity to present the Pro-Enrich project at the conference (Picture 9) and engage in dialogue with the participants as well as hand out project brochures. DTI also had a presentation at the event by Angelica Tamayo Tenorio.

Picture 9. Angelica Tamayo Tenorio, DTI, presenting Pro-Enrich at Circular Bioeconomy Days event, 2019.

Picture 10. Dissemination manger, Kell Andersen, Agro Business Park was moderator at the Danish Bioeconomy Conference 2019 and presented the Pro-Enrich project.

Due to the corona pandemic, the following scheduled events were cancelled/postponed:

- Event in Cardiff linked to the Vanguard Initiative and showcasing ongoing EU projects. Cancelled due to covid-19 - new date TBC (2E)
- Event in the Welsh Parliament (Senedd) - highlighting successful EU R&D projects. Mark Drakeford (First Minister) will open the event. Cancelled due to covid-19 - new date TBC (2E).

4.3. Industries

Pro-Enrich partners have participated in several events where the main audience is industry. The events include:

- Vitafoods Europe, May 7th - 9th, 2019, Geneva, Switzerland (3A)
- LIGNA FAIR 2019, May 27th - 31st, 2019, Hannover, Germany (3A) (Picture 11)
- Poster presentation at the international conference "Plant proteins in foods and diets", May 21st, 2019, Sorø, Denmark (3A)
- Poster presentation (ABP) and PPT presentation (DTI) at "Circular Bioeconomy Days", May 27th, 2019, Foulum, Denmark (3A)
- NORTH WALES BUSINESS EXHIBITION 2019, October 30th, 2019, Deeside, Wales, UK (3A)
- Danish Bioeconomy Conference 2019 (Dansk Bioøkonomi Konference) - Roll-up and distribution of brochure and fact-sheet + showing rapeseed protein concentrate, September 25th, 2019, Sakskøbing, Denmark (3A)
- BBI JU - Projects Day. Pro-Enrich was presented at exhibition booth 7B with roll-up, brochure and fact-sheet, December 3rd, 2019, Brussels, Belgium (3A)
- BBI JU Stakeholder Forum. Pro-Enrich was presented at exhibition booth 7B with roll-up, brochure and fact-sheet, December 4th, 2019, Brussels, Belgium (3A) (Picture 11)
- NutriFair exhibitions and tradeshow. Pro-Enrich was presented at the booths of both ABP and Emmelev, January 21st, 2020, Fredericia, Denmark (3A) (Picture 13+14)

One example of the dissemination activities that targeted the industry was the BBI JU Stakeholder Forum. The Stakeholder Forum is a one-day public event that brings together the bio-based industries community and facilitates open discussion on the impact, achievements and strategic direction of the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) programme, as well as the latest developments in the bio-based industries sector. Both Kell Andersen, Agro Business Park, and Irene Paredes, Innovarum, represented Pro-Enrich at the event (Picture 12).

The Stakeholder Forum was attended by more than 750 people from all over Europe and the Pro-Enrich booth attracted a lot of attention. The event was very beneficial and contributed to exchange knowledge, ideas, and best practices with other BBI JU grant recipients.

The day before (3rd of December 2019), the BBI JU organised the "Projects Day", dedicated exclusively to BBI JU funded projects. Both Kell and Irene also participated in this event.

Picture 11. Chimar promotes the Pro-Enrich project to visitors at their booth at LIGNA FAIR 2019.

Picture 12. Irene Paredes, Innovarum, and Kell Andersen, Agro Business Park, at the Pro-Enrich stand at BBI JU stakeholder Forum in December 2019.

Picture 13 & 14. Pro-Enrich promoted at Emmelev's (left) and Agro Business Park's (right) respective booths at NutriFair 2020.

4.4. Existing networks

Pro-Enrich partners have been in contact with several relevant networks and organisations. The networks and organisations that have been contacted include:

- Chil.org
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (Picture 15)
- LIAISON
- Welsh Government (Picture 16+17)
- North Wales Regional Engagement Team
- Partnership for sustainable biorefining (Partnerskab for Bæredygtig Bioraffinering)

One example of a dissemination activity that targeted relevant networks and organisations was a meeting with United Nations Development Programme (UNDP).

In June 2019, Dissemination manager Kell Andersen and Exploitation manager Lars Horsholt Jensen, Agro Business Park, met with UNDP's Nordic Representation Office in Copenhagen (Figure 15). They presented the Pro-Enrich project and how the project contributes to individual Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were discussed.

Picture 15. Kell Andersen and Lars Horsholt Jensen in front of the UN building in Copenhagen, Denmark, before a meeting with UNDP's Nordic Representation Office.

Another event attended by project partner, Bangor University was the Welsh government's Horizon 2020 Annual Event, which was held on July 4th, 2019, in Cardiff (Picture 16+17). The event explored how research and innovation funds in Wales, the UK and the EU can work together to boost Wales' international competitiveness.

Panel members:

- Patrick Child, European Commission
- Graham Allardice, Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy
- Nia Lewis, International Relations, Welsh Government
- Wyn Meredith, Compound Semiconductor Centre
- Liana Cipcigan, Cardiff University
- Martin Edlund, Minesto AB
- Baudewijn Morgan, Horizon 2020 Unit, Welsh Government

As part of the program a video was shown in which the Pro-Enrich project was featured. See the video here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Na5s99xsg8U>. Pro-Enrich is mentioned between minutes 7:55 to 11:14.

Picture 16 & 17. Shots from the video shown at Welsh Gov H2020 annual event showing Bangor University participants; Adam Charlton, WP3 leader (top) and Paul Baker in the laboratory (bottom).

4.5. Political organizations

Pro-Enrich partners have been involved in three activities where the target audience has been political organizations or politicians:

- Visit by a delegation from Ministry of Energy, Utilities and Climate, May 20th, 2019, at DTI, Taastrup, Denmark
- Visit by Mai Mercado, Minister for Children and Social Security, May 29th, 2019, at Emmlev, Otterup, Denmark.
- Visit by a delegation from Ministry of Higher Education and Science, October 8th, 2019, at DTI, Taastrup, Denmark

The delegation visits by both the Ministry of Energy, Utilities and Climate and the Ministry of Higher Education and Science included a presentation of the Pro-Enrich project as well as tour of the pilot-scale biorefinery plant at DTI. The meeting gave a unique opportunity to talk to the government officials and present them with current research on potential technologies for new sustainable bioeconomy solutions to the challenges of efficient bioresource utilization.

The visit by Mai Mercado, Minister for Children and Social Security, at project partner Emmelev included at presentation of the Pro-Enrich project and showed that Emmelev has a strong focus on sustainability and new business opportunities.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

During the project period May 2019 to April 2020 (M13 to M24) the Pro-Enrich partnership has conducted and participated in a significant number of relevant events and dissemination activities. The activities and events include

- Two general assemblies
- A periodic project review meeting
- Dissemination activities targeting Pro-Enrich stakeholders

The two general assemblies were hosted by project partners Tate & Lyle (Lübeck, Germany) and InnoRenew (Koper, Slovenia) respectively. During the general assemblies Pro-Enrich partners were updated on food and beverage solutions, sweeteners, stabilisation and functional systems, customer demands, market trends and bio-based solutions (Lübeck, Germany) and raw materials, olive processing, side-streams logistics and analysis possibilities (Koper, Slovenia).

A periodic project review meeting was conducted in January 2020. In addition to review of the project, input from BBI JU project officer, external experts and the BBI communication team provided valuable input on ways of increasing the impact of the project as well as the results generated in the project

A large number of dissemination activities have been conducted targeting different stakeholders including the general public, the research and scientific community, industries, networks and political organizations. The many activities have contributed significantly to maximizing the impact of the project. Unfortunately, in March and April 2020, due to the corona pandemic, a number of planned dissemination activities were either cancelled or postponed.

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Project partners

